

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) 241202xt_1

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: 241202xt_1

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0046 Å Wavelength=1.54178

Cell: a=5.9987(1) b=16.2643(3) c=21.1634(4)
 alpha=90 beta=90 gamma=90

Temperature: 296 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	2064.80(6)	2064.80(6)
Space group	P 21 21 21	P 21 21 21
Hall group	P 2ac 2ab	P 2ac 2ab
Moiety formula	C23 H22 F N O3	C23 H22 F N O3
Sum formula	C23 H22 F N O3	C23 H22 F N O3
Mr	379.42	379.41
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.220	1.221
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.710	0.710
F000	800.0	800.0
F000'	802.56	
h, k, lmax	7, 19, 25	7, 19, 25
Nref	3933[2285]	3888
Tmin, Tmax	0.886, 0.965	0.430, 0.753
Tmin'	0.886	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.430 Tmax=0.753
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.70/0.99 Theta(max)= 70.113

R(reflections)= 0.0442(3387)

wR2(reflections)=
0.1146(3888)

S = 1.051

Npar= 256

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low	'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	C20	Check		
PLAT340_ALERT_3_C	Low	Bond Precision on C-C Bonds	0.00461	Ang.		
PLAT910_ALERT_3_C	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).		6	Note		
	0 2 0,	0 1 1,	0 2 1,	0 0 2,	0 1 2,	0 1 3,
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L=	0.600	24	Report		
	1 1 0,	1 2 0,	1 3 0,	0 4 0,	0 6 0,	1 0 1,
	1 1 1,	1 3 1,	0 4 1,	1 4 1,	0 5 1,	1 0 2,
	1 1 2,	0 4 2,	0 19 2,	1 0 3,	0 2 3,	1 3 3,
	0 1 4,	0 1 5,	1 0 6,	0 5 9,	0 0 20,	0 0 24,
PLAT913_ALERT_3_C	Missing # of Very Strong Reflections in FCF		11	Note		
	0 2 0,	1 3 0,	0 4 0,	0 1 1,	1 1 1,	1 3 1,
	0 4 1,	1 4 1,	0 2 3,	0 1 4,	1 0 6,	

● **Alert level G**

PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O1	.	103.4	Degree
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C1	(Sohncke SpGr)		R Verify
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G	The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value		2.042	Note
	Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2	5.61 or SHELX Weight	10.91	
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.		0	Info
PLAT992_ALERT_5_G	Repd & Actual _reflns_number_gt Values Differ by		3	Check

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
5 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
5 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
3 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
4 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
1 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

